

Synthesis of A-Aza Triterpenes-I⁺ : A-Aza Triterpenes from Methyl Oleanonate, Methyl betulonate and Lupenone

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Schmidt reaction of methyl oleanonate (I), methyl betulonate (II) and lupenone (III) (in glacial acetic acid containing a few drops of Conc. $H_2SO_4 + NaN_3$) gave lactams (IA, IIA & IIIA). Beckmann rearrangement of their oximes (IB, IIB & IIIB) at 30°-35° with $POCl_3$ -Pyridine and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride-pyridine furnished the lactams (IA, IIA & IIIA) and 3, 4-seco-nitriles (IC, IIC & IIIC). Beckmann rearrangement with the same catalysts at 120° gave exclusively 3, 4-seco-nitriles. The lactams (IA, IIA & IIIA) were converted into 3, 4-seco-nitriles when refluxed with $POCl_3$ -pyridine.

SCHMIDT reaction of steroidal ketones and Beckmann rearrangement of their oximes were conducted to prepare Aza steroids¹⁻⁴. These reactions have not been extensively studied in the triterpenes. Even the few Beckmann rearrangements carried out with triterpenes were done with a view to prepare naturally occurring 3, 4-seco-carboxylic acid⁵⁻⁷.

The present investigation deals with the Schmidt reaction of methyl oleanonate (I), methyl betulonate (II) and lupenone (III) and Beckmann rearrangement of their oximes (IB, IIB, and IIIB). The ketones (I, II, III) in glacial acetic acid containing a few drops of conc. H_2SO_4 on treatment with NaN_3 gave lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA). The NMR spectrum of the lactam (IA) exhibited a signal at 5.5 δ (-NH-exchangeable with D_2O).

TABLE I—IR. SPECTRA OF THE LACTAMS AND 3, 4-SECO-NITRILES.

Compound	-NH	-CONH	-CN
IA	3220 cm^{-1}	1675 cm^{-1}	—
IC	—	—	2230 cm^{-1}
IIA	3075 cm^{-1} & 3225 cm^{-1}	1675 cm^{-1}	—
IIC	—	—	2235 cm^{-1}
IIIA	3075 cm^{-1} & 3230 cm^{-1}	1675 cm^{-1}	—
IIIC	—	—	2235 cm^{-1}

Beckmann rearrangement of the oximes (IB, IIB and IIIB) at 30°-35° with $POCl_3$ -pyridine and *p*-toluenesulphonylchloride-pyridine, followed by chromatography

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over alumina afforded lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA) and the corresponding 3, 4-seco-nitriles (IC, IIC and IIIC). Reactions with *p*-toluene sulphonylchloride-pyridine furnished besides the expected lactams and nitriles, a small quantity of the ketones (I, II and III), probably a part of the oxime is undergoing hydrolysis. Beckmann rearrangement of the oximes (IB, IIB and IIIB) conducted at 120° with the above catalysts gave exclusively the 3, 4-seco-nitriles (IC, IIC and IIIC).

The lactams obtained both in the Schmidt reaction and Beckmann rearrangement are identical (TLC & IR). The lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA) when refluxed with POCl₃-pyridine were converted into the corresponding 3, 4-seco-nitriles (IC, IIC and IIIC).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. I.R. Spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 Spectrophotometer. The N.M.R. spectrum was run on 60 MHz varian spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard.

Schmidt reaction of the ketones : (I, II and III) : (A typical experiment is detailed. Table 2 gives the details of the individual lactams.)

To a solution of the ketone in glacial acetic acid (1 g in 30-40 ml), conc. H₂SO₄ (0.3 to 0.4 ml) was added and kept in a bath maintained at 65°-70°. To this NaN₃ (0.5 g) was added in parts during 30 min with occasional stirring. After the addition of NaN₃ the reaction mixture was kept at 30° for 12 hr. poured into ice-cold Na₂CO₃ solution and extracted with ether. The residue obtained on removal of ether was adsorbed

washing the ether extract with dil. HCl. The residue obtained on removal of the solvent was adsorbed over alumina column and eluted with benzene and chloroform. Benzene eluate gave the 3, 4-seco-nitrile. The nitriles (IC, IIC and IIIC) crystallise from methanol as colourless crystals (yield 1.0 mg). Chloroform eluate gave the lactam. The lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA) crystallise from methanol or acetone as colourless crystals (yield 400 mg.)

(ii) To the oxime (1 g) in pyridine (30 ml freshly distilled) *p*-toluene sulphonylchloride (1 g) was added, kept at 30°-35° for 18 hr and poured into cold water and worked-up as above.

Benzene eluate showed 2 spots on TLC, so it was adsorbed over alumina column and eluted with *n*-hexane and benzene. The *n*-hexane eluate gave 3,4 seco-nitrile (yield 80 mg) and the benzene eluate gave the original ketone.

Chloroform eluate gave the lactam. The lactams obtained in the Schmidt reaction and the Beckmann rearrangement are identical (TLC and I.R.)

The Beckmann rearrangement was conducted with POCl₃-pyridine and *p*-toluene sulphonylchloride-pyridine at 120°, by refluxing in an oil bath for 3 hr and worked up as above.

The benzene eluate gave the 3,4-seco-nitrile (yield 500 mg for 1 g of the oxime). The chloroform eluate did not yield any residue.

TABLE 2—DETAILS OF THE LACTAMS AND 3, 4-SECO-NITRILES

Compound	M. P.	Molecular formula.	C	% of Elements				
				found H	N	C	required H	N.
IA	258°	C ₃₁ H ₄₉ O ₃ N	77.2	10.2	3.1	77.0	10.2	2.9
IC	144°	C ₃₁ H ₄₇ O ₂ N	79.9	10.0	3.0	80.0	10.1	3.0
IIA	256°	C ₃₁ H ₄₉ O ₃ N	77.1	9.9	2.8	77.0	10.2	2.9
IIC	140°	C ₃₁ H ₄₇ O ₂ N	79.9	10.1	3.0	80.0	10.1	3.0
IIIA	258°	C ₃₀ H ₄₉ ON	82.0	10.9	3.2	82.0	11.1	3.2
IIIC	154°	C ₃₀ H ₄₇ N	85.2	11.3	3.4	85.4	11.2	3.3

over alumina and eluted with chloroform. The chloroform eluate gave the lactam. The lactams (IA, IIA and IIIA) crystallise from acetone or methanol as colourless needles (yield 600 mg).

Beckmann Rearrangement of the oximes (IB, IIB and IIIB) : (Typical experiments one with each of the catalysts is described. Table 2 gives the details of the products of the rearrangement)

(i) The oxime (1 gm) was dissolved in pyridine (30 ml. freshly distilled over KOH) and POCl₃ (1 ml) was added drop by drop cooling the reaction mixture in ice. After the addition of POCl₃ the reaction mixture was kept at 30°-35° for 4 hr., poured into cold water, extracted with ether and the pyridine was removed by

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